

JAVASCRIPT FUNCTIONS - JAVASCRIPT FUNKSIYALAR HAQIDA BILISHINGIZ KERAK BO'LGAN KO'NIKMALAR

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301 – MI guruh talabasi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7937196>

Anotatsiya: Funktsiyalar JavaScriptda oddiy yoki nomlangan funktsiyalar sifatida yaratilishi mumkin. Oddiy funktsiyalar uning nomi bilan yaratiladi, nomlangan funktsiyalar esa boshqa o'zgaruvchilarga yozilgan funktsiyalar.

Kalit so'zlar: JavaScript, o'zgaruvchi, Oddiygina Funktsiya, Anonim funktsiya.

Аннотация: Функции могут быть созданы в JavaScript как простые или именованные функции. Простые функции создаются по их имени, а именованные функции — это функции, записанные в другие переменные.

Ключевые слова: JavaScript, переменная, простая функция, анонимная функция.

Abstract: Functions can be created in JavaScript as simple or named functions. Simple functions are created by their name, while named functions are functions written to other variables.

Keywords: JavaScript, Variable, Simple Function, Anonymous Function.

Funktsiyalar Javascriptning eng asosiy tushunchalaridir biri hisoblanadi. Dasturlashni endi o'rganayotganlar uchun Funktsiyalar biroz qiyindek tuyulishi mumkin, sababi funktsiyalar turli ko'rinishlarda keladi. Ushbu tezisda Javascript da funktsiyani ta'riflash yo'llari va ularni qo'llanilishni batafsil yoritamiz.

Tezisni yaxshilab o'qib, tushunib, o'zlashtirib olsangiz, keyin React va Angular kabi framework larni o'rganishingizda katta foyda beradi. Ushbu tezisni davom ettirishdan avval, Javascript Object haqidagi tezismni o'qishni tavsiya qilaman.

Funktsiya o'zi nima?

Javascript da funktsiya, bu buyruqlarni ketma ketlikda bajaradigan sintaksar to'plami desak ham bo'ladi.

Oddiygina Funktsiya: Oddiygina funktsiya 'function' kalit so'zi, undan keyin funktsiyaga berilgan nom, qavs (), va qiyshiq qavs {} dan tashkil topadi. Qavs ichiga funktsiyada ishlatidagidan parameter lar yoziladi (pastroqda parameter lar haqida), qiyshiq qavs {} ichi esa funktsiyaning asosiy qismi hisoblanadi, va bajarilishi kerak bo'lgan buyruqlar shuning ichida yoziladi. Misolda ko'ramiz:

```
// FUNCTION DECLARATION - funktsiyani yasash, ushbu misolda parameterlarsiz
```

```
// Function kalit so'zi funktsiyaning nomi bilan birga keladi
```

```
// Funktsiya nomidan keyin qavs (), ixtiyoriy parameter larni oladi
```

```
// Qiyshiq qavs {} ichidagilar esa funktsiyaning asosiy qismi hisoblanadi
```

```
function sovuq(){
```

```
    console.log("Xalqga gaz va elektr bering");
```

```
}
```

```
// funktsiyani ishga tushirish esa uning nomi va qavs ni yozish orqali bo'ladi
```

```
sovuq(); // natija => Xalqga gaz va elektr bering
```

```
// FUNCTION DECLARATION - 1ta parameter bilan;
// Qavs () 1ta parameter qabul qilgandagi holati
// Backticks orqali `` biz var nomini string ichida ishlata olamiz.
// `` ichida var nomini ${var_nomi} orqali ishlatish ES6 xususiyatlaridan biri
```

```
function bering(xalqmulki) {
  console.log(`Xalqga ${xalqmulki}ni bering`);
}
// bering() funksiyasini ishga tushirish
bering('gaz'); // natija: Xalqga gazni bering
```

```
function trendGaplar(trend1, trend2){
  console.log(`Bu yildagi trend bo'lgan gaplar: ${trend1} va ${trend2}`)
}
trendGaplar('5600 som', 'kop gosht'); // natija: Bu yildagi trend bo'lgan gaplar: 5600 som va kop gosht
```

Funksiya o'zidan biron qiymat ham qaytarishi mumkin, 'return'

Yuqoridagi funksiyalarda funksiya {} ichidagi buyruqlarni bajarganini ko'rdik. Endi esa o'zidan value (qiymat) qaytaradigan 'return' funksiyaga qaraymiz.

// 'color' parameter ni oluvchi oddiy funksiya

```
function nameFruitByColor(color) {
  if(color === 'red') {
    return 'apple';
  } else if (color === 'yellow') {
    return 'banana';
  } else if (color === 'green') {
    return 'watermelon';
  }
}
```

// nameFruitByColor funksiyadan qaytadigan qiymatni console da chiqarib berish:

```
console.log(nameFruitByColor('red')); // natija: apple
console.log(nameFruitByColor('yellow')); // natija: banana
```

Yuqoridagan funksiyadan biz oddiygina string value qaytardik (return). Aslida esa, nafaqat string, istalgan data, ya'ni string, number, object, boolean, array va boshqalarni return qilsa bo'ladi.

Anonim funksiya: Agar funksiyaning o'ziga nom berilmasdan, funksiya const yoki let ga qiymat qilib berilgan bo'lsa, bunday funksiya anonim (Anonymous) funksiya deb nomlanadi. Anonim funksiya variable ga qiymat qilib berilgan bo'lishi shart.

// Anonim funksiya yasashda e'tibor berish kerak bo'lgan jihatlar

// Funksiya nomi yozilmaydi

// funksiya 'fullName' variable ga qiymat qilib berilgan

```
const fullName = function (firstName, lastName) {
  return `The full Name is ${firstName} ${lastName}`
}
```

```
// Agar 'fullName' o'zini console.log ichiga qo'ysak,
// bizga butun funksiyani console da chiqarib beradi
console.log(fullName);
// Agar hech qanday parameter siz console.log ga qo'ysak
console.log(fullName()); // natija => 'The Full Name is undefined undefined'
// Agar berilgan parameter larga qiymat berib console.log ga chiqarsak
console.log('John','Smith'); // natija => The Full Name is John Smith
// Anonim funksiya yasashda e'tibor berish kerak bo'lgan jihatlar
// Funksiya nomi yozilmaydi
// funksiya 'fullName' variable ga qiymat qilib berilgan
const fullName = function (firstName, lastName) {
  return `The full Name is ${firstName} ${lastName}`
}
// Agar 'fullName' o'zini console.log ichiga qo'ysak,
// bizga butun funksiyani console da chiqarib beradi
console.log(fullName);
// Agar hech qanday parameter siz console.log ga qo'ysak
console.log(fullName()); // natija => 'The Full Name is undefined undefined'
// Agar berilgan parameter larga qiymat berib console.log ga chiqarsak
console.log('John','Smith'); // natija => The Full Name is John Smith
```

Yuqoridagi syntax 'function expression' deb ham ataladi. Va 'fullName' ni funksiya nomi deb ham qarasa bo'ladi.

Xulosalar:

Phone funksiyasi 3ta parameter qabul qiladi, va qachonki new Phone orqali yangi object yasalganda, ushbu 3ta parameter yangi object ning property siga aylanadi. (albatta komputerdan yozib ko'rib, console da o'zingiz uchun natijani ko'ring) Constructor funksiyadan Object yasash uchun 'new' kalit so'zi ishlatilishi shart 'this' kalit so'zi Phone ga ishora qiladi. Ya'ni qachonki `iphoneX = new Phone('Apple', 'iPhoneX', 'Black')` ishga tushganida, 'Apple' parameter Phone ning 'make' property si qiymatiga aylanadi. iPhoneX esa 'mode' property. Xuddi shu usulda note20 va onePlus7 ham

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